

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF CHEMICAL INTERACTION AND GLASS FORMATION IN THE As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 SYSTEM

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Abstract

The chemical interaction and glass transition in the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system were studied using the methods of physicochemical analysis: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray phase analysis (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as density and microhardness measurements, and the T-x phase diagram was constructed. It was found that the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system is a quasi-binary section of the quasi-ternary system As_2Se_3 - Ga_2S_3 - Tl_2Te and belongs to the eutectic type. The binary eutectic formed between the As_2Se_3 and TlGaTe_2 components has a composition of 25 mol % TlGaTe_2 and a temperature of 260°C. According to the results of the microstructural analysis, it was found that the region of the solid solution based on As_2Se_3 reaches up to 2 mol % TlGaTe_2 , and 10 mol % As_2Se_3 is dissolved based on the TlGaTe_2 compound. In the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system, a glass region containing 15 mol % TlGaTe_2 based on the As_2Se_3 compound was determined upon slow cooling.

Keywords: phase equilibrium, quasi-binary, eutectic, density, glass.

Introduction

The components of the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system are substances studied as semiconductors with functional properties. It is known that arsenic chalcogenides are semiconductor compounds obtained in the form of normal-valence glass. First of all, the study of the physicochemical properties of arsenic compounds with chalcogenides is associated with the expansion of their practical application.

Arsenic chalcogenides, their compounds and glassy alloys are materials with high photoelectric [1-6], luminescent [7,8] and acousto-optic [9] properties.

In recent years, chalcogenide fibers [10-12] based on As_2S_3 and As_2Se_3 have been used to transmit light in the mid-IR range and have found application as a compact nonlinear medium that allows for Raman amplification [13] and laser generation [14]. We have investigated systems devoted to the chemical interaction of compounds of the As_2X_3 and TlGaX_2 (X-S,Se) type [15-18]. The quaternary system As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 has not yet been investigated. The aim of this work is to study the chemical interaction and glass formation in the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system with the construction of the T-x phase diagram and the determination of the solid solution regions. The As_2Se_3 compound melts congruently at 381°C and crystallizes in the monoclinic syngony with the lattice parameters: $a=12.053$; $b=9890$; $c=4.277$ Å, $\alpha=90^\circ 28'$, sp. gr. P21/n has a glass density of $\rho=4.62$ g/cm³, microhardness $H\mu=140$ MPa, crystal density of $\rho=5.21$ g/cm³, microhardness $H\mu=75$ MPa [19].

The TlGaTe_2 compound melts congruently at 775°C and crystallizes in the tetragonal syngony with the unit cell parameters: $a=8.22$; $c=7.10$ Å, $z=4$, density

and microhardness $\rho=7.32$ g/cm³ and 900 MPa, respectively [20].

Experimental part

The components As_2Se_3 and TlGaTe_2 of the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system were synthesized from elements of the following purity: As-99.999%, Tl-99.998%, Ga-99.999% and sulfur of the OSCh grade. The alloys of the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system were synthesized from the components As_2Se_3 and TlGaTe_2 by the method of fusion in quartz ampoules in the temperature range of 500-800°C at a pressure of 0.133 Pa. Then the alloys were subjected to heat treatment for 240 hours at a temperature of 260°C for their homogenization. Alloys of the As_2Se_3 - TlGaTe_2 system were studied using the methods of physicochemical analysis: differential-thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray phase analysis (XPA), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as density and microhardness measurements. Differential-thermal analysis (DTA) was performed on a THERMOSCAN-2 thermograph. The Al_2O_3 compound was taken as a standard, the heating rate was 5°C/min.

X-ray phase analysis was performed on a D2-PHASER X-ray diffractometer. $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation and a Ni filter were used in the study.

Microstructural analysis (MSA) was performed on a MIM-8 microscope. For this, the alloys were polished and polished, and their structure was studied under a microscope. Microhardness was measured with a PMT-3 metallographic hardness tester. For each phase, the dependence of microhardness on composition was measured. The density of the samples was determined by the pycnometric method using toluene as a filling solution.

Fig. 1. Microstructures of $As_2Se_3-TlGaTe_2$ alloys.
1-15 mol %, 2-25 mol %, 3-50 mol %, 4-90 mol % $TlGaTe_2$.

The microstructure of the glassy sample of 15 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ appears matte and single-phase. The sample with a concentration of 25 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ is a eutectic composition consisting of a glass-crystalline mixture. The sample of 50 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ is a two-phase field alloy. The single-phase sample containing 90 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ is a solid solution alloy based on the $TlGaTe_2$ compound.

X-ray phase analysis was performed for samples of the $As_2Se_3-TlGaTe_2$ system containing 5, 15, 50 and 90 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ (Fig. 2). As can be seen from the

figure, no diffraction lines are observed in the diffraction patterns of 5 and 15 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ alloys, which means that these samples are glassy alloys. The diffraction lines in the diffraction pattern of the 50 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ alloy consist of a mixture of diffraction lines of its main components and are a two-phase alloy. The diffraction pattern of the 90 mol % $TlGaTe_2$ alloy is identical to the diffraction pattern of the $TlGaTe_2$ compound, i.e. the sample is a solid solution alloy based on the $TlGaTe_2$ compound.

Fig. 2. Diffraction patterns of alloys of the $As_2Se_3-TlGaTe_2$ system.
1- As_2Se_3 , 2-5, 3-15, 4-50, 5-90, 6-100 mol % $TlGaTe_2$.

Thus, the X-ray phase analysis confirms the results of differential thermal and microstructural analysis.

The T-x phase diagram of the $As_2Se_3-TlGaTe_2$ system is constructed based on the results of physico-chemical analysis methods (Fig. 3). The phase diagram

of the system is quasi-binary, eutectic type. The composition of the eutectic formed between the compounds As_2Se_3 and $TlGaTe_2$ is 25 mol % $TlGaTe_2$, the temperature is 260°C.

Fig. 3. Phase diagram of the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system.

The liquidus of the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system consists of monovariant equilibrium curves of the α-solid solution formed on the basis of the As₂Se₃ compound and the β-solid solution based on TlGaTe₂. In the system based on the As₂Se₃ compound, a field of the solid solution with a concentration of 2 mol % TlGaTe₂ is formed at room temperature, and on the basis of the TlGaTe₂ compound, the region of the solid solution is 10 mol % As₂Se₃. Below the solidus line in the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system, two-phase alloys consisting of (α + β) crystallize. The dependence of the microhardness of the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system alloys on the composition was studied. It was determined that there are two different values of microhardness. Some physicochemical properties of glassy alloys of 0-25 mol % TlGaTe₂ are given in Table 1. Table 2 shows some physicochemical properties of As₂Se₃ system alloys after heat treatment of

As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system alloys at 220°C for 500 hours. The microhardness of glassy alloys based on As₂Se₃ varies within the range of (1400-1490) MPa, and their density within the range of 4.62-5.29 g/cm³ (Table 1). The softening temperature T_g (140–180°C) is observed on the thermograms of 0–15 mol % TlGaTe₂ alloys.

The microhardness of α-solid solutions based on the As₂Se₃ composition in crystalline form varies within the range of (780-870) MPa. The microhardness value of (900-950) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of β-solid solutions based on TlGaTe₂. After crystallization of alloys with a content of 0–15 mol % TlGaTe₂, the softening temperature in the thermograms of the alloys is lost, and the temperature effects of the liquidus and solidus are retained (Table 2).

Table 1.

, DTA results, density and microhardness measurements alloys of the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system (in the glass)

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, q/sm ³	Microhardness, MPa	
As ₂ Se ₃	TlGaTe ₂			α	β
				P=0,10 N	P=0,15 N
100	0.0	140,381	4,62	1400	Glass
97	3,0	140,310,380	4,66	1460	Glass
95	5,0	145,275,375	4,70	1470	Glass
90	10	150,260,350	4,89	1480	Glass
85	15	170,260,325	5,03	1480	Glass
80	20	180,260,300	5,16	1480	Glass-crystal
75	25	180,260	5,29	1480	Glass-crystal

Composition, DTA results, density and microhardness measurements alloys of the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system (in the crystal)

Composition , mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, q/sm ³	Microhardness, MPa	
As ₂ Se ₃	TlGaTe ₂			α	β
				P=0,10 N	P=0,15 N
100	0.0	381	5,21	780	–
97	3,0	310,380	5,26	790	–
95	5,0	275,375	5,32	850	–
90	10	260,350	5,42	870	–
85	15	260,325	5,53	870	–
80	20	260,300	5,63	–	–
75	25	260	5,74	Eutec.	Eutec.
70	30	260,410	5,85	–	950
60	40	260,570	6,06	–	950
50	50	260,640	6,30	–	950
40	60	260,660	6,45	–	950
30	70	260,690	6,70	–	950
20	80	260,710	6,94	–	950
10	90	450,750	7,37	–	950
5,0	95	620,765	7,35	–	940
0,0	100	775	7,32	–	900

Conclusion

The methods of physicochemical analysis (DTA, X-ray diffraction of the microstructure of the MSA, as well as density and microhardness measurements) studied the chemical interaction and glass formation in the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system and constructed its phase diagram. The phase diagram of the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system is quasi-binary and eutectic. Joint crystallization of As₂Se₃ and TlGaTe₂ compounds ends at the double eutectic point, the composition is 25 mol % TlGaTe₂, the temperature is 260°C. It was found that the solid solution region based on the As₂Se₃ compound is 2 mol % TlGaTe₂, and based on the TlGaTe₂ compound, the solubility is 10 mol % As₂Se₃ at room temperature. With slow cooling in the As₂Se₃-TlGaTe₂ system, the glass area of 15 mol % TlGaTe₂ was determined. The glass-crystalline area varies within the range of 15-25 mol % TlGaTe₂.

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